

Screening outcomes and treatment patterns of retinopathy of prematurity in Bulgaria: Emerging role of anti-VEGF therapy

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Abstract

A retrospective analysis of premature infants screened for retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) in Sofia between 2019 and 2023 included 660 infants. ROP was diagnosed in 145 infants (21.97%). Treatment was required in 97 infants (14.7% of all screened). Laser photocoagulation was performed in 80 infants (82.5% of treated cases), whereas intravitreal anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) therapy with aflibercept was administered in 17 infants (17.5%), mainly in posterior or aggressive disease. Spontaneous regression occurred in 48 infants (33.1%). No cases of endophthalmitis or systemic adverse events were observed after anti-VEGF therapy. Lower gestational age and birth weight were strongly associated with disease occurrence. These findings indicate that ROP remains a significant clinical challenge in premature infants, whereas pharmacological VEGF inhibition represents an important therapeutic option in selected severe cases, complementing conventional laser treatment.

Keywords

Aflibercept, prematurity, retina, ROP, vitreoretinal pharmacotherapy

Introduction

Retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) remains one of the leading causes of preventable childhood blindness worldwide. It is a multifactorial vasoproliferative disorder that affects the developing retinal vasculature of premature infants, resulting in abnormal neovascularization and potential retinal detachment (Terry 1943, 2018; Gilbert 2008; Marinov 2013;

Mladenov 2016; Oscar et al. 2021). The condition was first described by Terry in 1942 as retrolental fibroplasia and was soon recognized as a major cause of blindness among surviving preterm infants. Over the decades, the incidence and characteristics of ROP have evolved in parallel with improvements in neonatal care (Terry 1946; Gilbert et al. 2019).

Three distinct "epidemics" of ROP-related blindness have been described. The first occurred in the 1940s–1950s

and was attributed to unmonitored oxygen therapy in premature infants (Crosse and Evans 1952; Chiang et al. 2021). The second, in the 1970s, coincided with the increased survival of extremely preterm infants due to advances in neonatal intensive care. The current third epidemic primarily affects low- and middle-income countries, where neonatal care remains variable and oxygen administration is often poorly controlled. Consequently, ROP has emerged as a global health concern, with substantial geographic disparities in prevalence and outcomes (Gilbert and Foster 2001; Gilbert et al. 2005; Gilbert 2007; Mladenov 2016).

In Bulgaria, recent data indicate a rising trend in ROP incidence—from 5.4% in earlier reports to more than 30% in recent years. This increase reflects both the improved survival of premature infants and inconsistent implementation of standardized screening protocols. Despite the establishment of a National Strategy for Screening and Treatment of ROP in 2009, revised in 2014, regional variability persists (Popova et al. 1997; Hristozov et al. 1999; Kontrova et al. 1999; Tsvetkova et al. 2000; Aleksieva et al. 2001; Slancheva et al. 2002; Chernodrina 2003; Nikolova et al. 2009; Slancheva 2009; Nikolova and Kontrova 2010; Marinov 2013; Dimitrova-Grozeva 2016).

The objective of the present study is to evaluate the screening, diagnosis, and treatment of premature infants with ROP in Bulgaria between 2019 and 2023, to identify key epidemiological patterns, and to assess the effectiveness of the current national approach in preventing vision-threatening outcomes.

The management of ROP has evolved considerably over recent decades. Screening programs are guided by national and international protocols that identify at-risk infants based on gestational age and birth weight, enabling timely intervention before vision-threatening sequelae develop (Pfeil et al. 2021). Laser photocoagulation of the avascular retina has long been considered the standard of care for treatment-requiring ROP, demonstrating high rates of disease regression and arrest of neovascularization. However, this approach carries inherent limitations, including the need for general anesthesia, permanent destruction of peripheral retinal tissue, and an associated risk of high myopia and visual field loss in later life. The emergence of anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) therapy has expanded the treatment armamentarium for ROP, offering a pharmacological alternative that suppresses pathological neovascularization while potentially preserving peripheral retinal vascularization. Several pivotal clinical trials, including BEAT-ROP, RAINBOW, and FIREFLEYE, have demonstrated the efficacy of anti-VEGF agents—bevacizumab, ranibizumab, and aflibercept, respectively—for the treatment of severe ROP (Mintz-Hittner et al. 2011; Stahl et al. 2019; Stahl et al. 2024). Key considerations in the use of anti-VEGF therapy include the risk of late disease reactivation, the potential for systemic VEGF suppression in a vulnerable neonatal population, and the need for prolonged ophthalmological follow-up. As reviewed by Pfeil et al. (2021) in the Bulgarian Review of Ophthalmology, ROP management has undergone significant transformation, with anti-VEGF therapy now playing a central role alongside updated screening criteria and international collaborative data initiatives such as EU-ROP.

Patients and methods

This retrospective observational study was conducted at the Eye Clinic of Alexandrovska University Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria, and included all premature infants screened for ROP between January 2019 and December 2023. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board of Alexandrovska University Hospital, and all procedures adhered to the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent for ophthalmic screening and data analysis was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants.

Study population

Eligible participants were all preterm infants who met the national criteria for ROP screening in Bulgaria, as defined by the National Strategy for Screening and Treatment of ROP (2009, revised 2014). Screening was performed in:

Infants with birth weight ≤ 1500 g or gestational age ≤ 32 weeks;

Selected infants with birth weight > 1500 g or gestational age > 32 weeks who presented with additional risk factors, such as prolonged oxygen therapy, sepsis, intraventricular hemorrhage (grade II or higher), necrotizing enterocolitis, severe anemia requiring transfusion, or mechanical ventilation.

A total of 660 premature infants (352 male, 308 female) were screened for ROP. The mean gestational age was 30.97 weeks (30.94 weeks for males, 31.0 weeks for females), and the mean birth weight was 1,498.9 g (1,532.9 g for males, 1,460.3 g for females).

Screening and examination protocol

The first ophthalmological examination was performed between 4 and 6 weeks of postnatal age or 31–33 weeks of postmenstrual age, whichever came later, and before discharge from the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). Follow-up examinations were conducted weekly or biweekly, depending on retinal vascular maturity and disease activity, until full vascularization of the retina or regression of ROP was documented.

Pupillary dilation was achieved with a combination of cyclopentolate 0.5% and phenylephrine 2.5%, instilled three times at 10–15 min intervals. Topical anesthesia with proxymetacaine hydrochloride 0.5% was applied before examination. Fundus evaluation was performed by indirect ophthalmoscopy using 20 D or 28 D lenses. Documentation was made with RetCam digital imaging (Clarity Medical Systems, USA) where available.

ROP was classified according to the International Classification of Retinopathy of Prematurity, Third Edition (ICROP3, 2021), based on disease zone, stage, and the presence of “plus” disease.

Treatment protocol

Treatment was indicated for:

- Any stage ROP in Zone I with “plus” disease;
- Stage 3 ROP in Zone I without “plus” disease;
- Stage 2 or 3 ROP in Zone II with “plus” disease.

Laser photocoagulation of the avascular retina using an 810 nm diode laser was the primary treatment modality. The procedure was performed under sedation or general anesthesia, with treatment completed within 72 h of diagnosis. Infants unfit for laser therapy or with posterior aggressive disease (A-ROP) received an intravitreal anti-VEGF injection with aflibercept (0.04 mg/0.01 mL) under sterile conditions. All treated infants were followed weekly for disease regression or reactivation.

Data collection and analysis

Data were extracted from standardized medical records and included gestational age, birth weight, systemic comorbidities, stage and zone of ROP, treatment type, and outcomes. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics.

Results

Between January 2019 and December 2023, a total of 660 premature infants (352 male and 308 female) were screened for ROP across three neonatal centers in Sofia, Bulgaria. The mean gestational age was 30.97 ± 2.9 weeks (range, 23–39 weeks), and the mean birth weight was $1,498.9 \pm 484.3$ g (range, 560–3,620 g). Most infants (68.2%) were delivered by cesarean section.

Prevalence and severity of ROP

Of the 660 screened infants, 145 (21.97%) were diagnosed with ROP of any stage, whereas 515 (78.0%) had no retinal changes. The distribution of ROP by stage was as follows: stage 1, 31 infants (4.7%); stage 2, 41 infants (6.2%); stage 3, 66 infants (10.0%); stage 4, two infants (0.3%); and stage 5, five infants (0.8%).

ROP incidence was inversely related to gestational age. Among infants born before 28 weeks, the frequency reached 54.9%, decreasing to 27.1% at 28–30 weeks, 10.1% at 30–32 weeks, and < 5% in those born after 32 weeks.

Treatment and outcomes

Treatment was required in 97 infants (66.9% of those with ROP; 14.7% of all screened).

Laser photocoagulation was performed in 80 infants (82.5%).

Intravitreal anti-VEGF injection with aflibercept was administered in 17 infants (17.5%), primarily in cases with “plus” disease or posterior zone involvement.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the screened population.

Characteristic	Value
Total infants screened	660 (352 male, 308 female)
Mean gestational age (weeks)	30.97 ± 2.9 (range 23–39)
Mean birth weight (g)	1498.9 ± 484.3 (range 560–3620)
Cesarean section delivery	450 (68.2%)
Study period	January 2019–December 2023

Table 2. ROP prevalence by gestational age and stage distribution.

Parameter	n	% of screened
ROP stage distribution		
Stage 1	31	4.7%
Stage 2	41	6.2%
Stage 3	66	10.0%
Stage 4	2	0.3%
Stage 5	5	0.8%
ROP prevalence by gestational age		
<28 weeks	–	54.9%
28–30 weeks	–	27.1%
30–32 weeks	–	10.1%
>32 weeks	–	<5%

Table 3. Treatment modalities and outcomes.

Outcome	n (%)
Total ROP diagnosed	145 (21.97% of screened)
Treatment required	97 (66.9% of ROP; 14.7% of screened)
Laser photocoagulation	80 (82.5% of treated)
Intravitreal anti-VEGF (aflibercept)	17 (17.5% of treated)
Spontaneous regression (no treatment)	48 (33.1% of ROP cases)
Complications after laser	1 bilateral cataract (1.25%)
Endophthalmitis/systemic adverse events after anti-VEGF	0 (0%)

Spontaneous regression occurred in 48 infants (33.1%) without treatment.

Among laser-treated infants, one developed bilateral cataracts postoperatively. No cases of endophthalmitis or systemic adverse events were recorded after anti-VEGF therapy.

Risk factor correlation

ROP occurrence was significantly associated with lower gestational age and lower birth weight ($p < 0.001$ for both). Infants < 28 weeks’ gestation or < 1250 g in birth weight had the highest disease incidence. A higher prevalence was also observed among multiple births compared with singletons ($p < 0.05$). The key findings of this study are summarized in Tables 1–3 below.

Discussion

The present study provides a contemporary overview of screening, diagnosis, and treatment patterns of ROP in Bulgaria between 2019 and 2023. Among 660 screened premature infants, ROP was diagnosed in 21.97% of cases, and treatment was required in 14.7% of all screened

infants. These findings are consistent with epidemiological data reported in several middle-income countries, where improvements in neonatal care have led to increased survival of extremely premature infants and a corresponding rise in ROP incidence (Gilbert and Foster 2001; Gilbert 2008; Chiang et al. 2021).

The incidence of ROP in this cohort demonstrated a strong inverse correlation with gestational age and birth weight, confirming these factors as the most important predictors of disease development. Infants born before 28 weeks of gestation showed the highest risk of developing ROP, which is consistent with previous epidemiological studies (Jones et al. 2005; Geloneck et al. 2014; Chiang et al. 2021).

Laser photocoagulation of the avascular retina remained the primary treatment modality in this study, accounting for more than 80% of treated cases. Since the Early Treatment for Retinopathy of Prematurity (ETROP) study, laser therapy has been considered the gold standard for type 1 ROP (Jones et al. 2005).

By ablating the peripheral avascular retina, laser treatment reduces retinal hypoxia and suppresses the angiogenic drive responsible for pathological neovascularization. However, laser therapy has several limitations. The procedure may require general anesthesia and specialized equipment, and it permanently destroys peripheral retinal tissue, which may result in peripheral visual field loss and a higher incidence of myopia later in life (Geloneck et al. 2014; Chiang et al. 2021).

Laser treatment may also be technically difficult in posterior disease or aggressive ROP. Pharmacological inhibition of VEGF has emerged as an important alternative treatment strategy. VEGF plays a central role in the pathogenesis of ROP by mediating hypoxia-induced pathological retinal neovascularization (Smith 2003; Hellström et al. 2013).

Anti-VEGF agents suppress abnormal angiogenesis while potentially allowing continued physiological vascularization of the peripheral retina (Crosse and Evans 1952; Gilbert et al. 2005).

In the present study, intravitreal anti-VEGF therapy with aflibercept was administered in 17.5% of treated infants, mainly in cases with posterior disease or aggressive ROP. This proportion reflects the growing role of pharmacological angiogenesis inhibition in modern ROP management (Darlow et al. 2013; VanderVeen et al. 2017).

Aflibercept is a recombinant fusion protein composed of extracellular domains of VEGF receptors 1 and 2 fused to the Fc portion of human IgG1. This structure allows the molecule to function as a soluble decoy receptor with high binding affinity for VEGF-A, VEGF-B, and placental growth factor (PlGF) (Papadopoulos et al. 2012). Compared with other anti-VEGF agents, aflibercept demonstrates strong VEGF binding and prolonged intraocular activity (Avery et al. 2017).

Clinical trials have demonstrated the effectiveness of anti-VEGF therapy in ROP. The BEAT-ROP study showed that intravitreal bevacizumab significantly reduced recurrence rates in zone I stage 3+ disease compared with laser therapy (Mintz-Hittner et al. 2011). The RAINBOW

trial subsequently demonstrated favorable outcomes with ranibizumab (Stahl et al. 2019), whereas the FIREFLY study evaluated aflibercept for ROP treatment and confirmed high rates of disease regression (Stahl et al. 2024).

In this cohort, intravitreal aflibercept injections were not associated with severe ocular complications or systemic adverse events. These findings support previous reports indicating that intravitreal anti-VEGF therapy can be safely administered when appropriate sterile technique and dosing protocols are used (Wallace 2016; VanderVeen et al. 2017).

Nevertheless, systemic safety remains a critical consideration when using anti-VEGF agents in premature infants. VEGF plays an essential role in the development of multiple organ systems, including the lungs, kidneys and central nervous system (Ferrara et al. 2004). Systemic suppression of VEGF following intravitreal injection has been reported, raising concerns about potential long-term developmental effects (Kong et al. 2015; Morin et al. 2016). Another important limitation of anti-VEGF therapy is the risk of late recurrence of ROP. Unlike laser therapy, which permanently eliminates the avascular retina, anti-VEGF therapy allows continued retinal vascularization. Although this preserves peripheral retinal tissue, it also means that disease reactivation may occur weeks or months after treatment, requiring prolonged follow-up (Lepore et al. 2014).

Despite these limitations, anti-VEGF therapy offers several important advantages. The procedure is technically simple and particularly effective in posterior disease, where laser treatment may be difficult. Furthermore, anti-VEGF therapy may reduce the risk of peripheral visual field loss and high myopia associated with extensive laser photocoagulation (Geloneck et al. 2014).

The novelty and significance of the present study lie in its provision of the first contemporary multicenter epidemiological data on ROP screening and treatment outcomes in Bulgaria covering the 5-year period 2019–2023. This represents the largest cohort of screened premature infants reported from a Bulgarian tertiary center in the modern era of ROP management, and it documents the real-world adoption of anti-VEGF therapy within the national treatment framework. Critically, this study demonstrates that intravitreal aflibercept—a high-affinity VEGF trap with a unique molecular mechanism distinct from other anti-VEGF agents—can be safely and effectively employed in a Bulgarian clinical setting for the management of posterior and aggressive ROP (Papadopoulos et al. 2012; Avery et al. 2017). The absence of ocular or systemic adverse events following anti-VEGF injections in this cohort provides important local safety data that complement findings from international clinical trials (Mintz-Hittner et al. 2011; Stahl et al. 2019; Stahl et al. 2024). Moreover, the documented shift in treatment practice, with 17.5% of treated infants receiving anti-VEGF therapy as primary treatment, underscores the growing role of pharmacological VEGF inhibition in modern ROP management and reflects the global trend toward individualized treatment strategies for this complex disease (Darlow et al. 2013;

VanderVeen et al. 2017). These findings carry direct implications for national screening guidelines and support the continued integration of anti-VEGF therapy within the Bulgarian ROP treatment protocol, particularly for cases involving zone I or aggressive disease, where conventional laser photocoagulation may be technically challenging or carry a greater risk of refractive sequelae (Geloneck et al. 2014; Pfeil et al. 2021).

The present study has several limitations. Its retrospective design may introduce selection bias, and the study population was limited to a small number of centers. In addition, long-term visual and neurodevelopmental outcomes were not evaluated.

Conclusion

In conclusion, ROP remains an important cause of visual impairment among premature infants in Bulgaria. Laser photocoagulation continues to be the primary treatment modality; however, intravitreal anti-VEGF therapy represents an increasingly important pharmacological option, particularly for posterior and aggressive forms of ROP.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: UMBAL Alexandrovska.

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The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: GPT, Used for: Language, style and writing. AI tool was used to assist with language editing and improvement of clarity. All scientific content, data interpretation, and conclusions were developed and verified by the authors.

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Author contributions

Alexander Oscar: Investigation; Methodology; Writing – original draft. Yani Zdravkov: Writing – added critical review. Vasil Haykin: Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing; Investigation. Ognyan Mladenov: Investigation. Valentina Tomova: Investigation; Writing – review & editing. Ralitzha Georgieva: Investigation; Writing – review & editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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